

Faris' Approach to convert integral to derivative

(1) Introduction

A curve line in a plane has some length and the area under the curve is given by integral. If you represent this area by lines and derive line length equation in which derivative is involved then integral is given in terms of derivative. That's the way to convert integral to derivative.

(Please remember this while reading this article $f(x)=y$).

(2) Basic Idea

The basic concept of integration and differentiation is explained as follows:

1. The Integral Equation

$$\lim_{\Delta x \rightarrow 0} \sum_{x=a}^b y \Delta x = \int_a^b y dx$$

2. The Derivative Equation

$$\lim_{\Delta x \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta y}{\Delta x} = \frac{dy}{dx}$$

(3) Conversion of Integral to Derivative

First derive an equation of line length in terms of derivative. Secondly representing area or integral with lines. Thirdly combine these two steps which is called Faris' Approach.

1. Line Length and derivative

Physically: Pythagoras Theorem represents right angle triangle hypotenuse line length. Suppose a very small hypotenuse in which Δx is approaching zero.

Mathematically:

$$\begin{aligned} l^2 &= \Delta x^2 + \Delta y^2 \\ l &= \Delta x \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{\Delta y}{\Delta x}\right)^2} \\ l &= \lim_{\Delta x \rightarrow 0} \Delta x \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{\Delta y}{\Delta x}\right)^2} \\ l &= dx \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{dy}{dx}\right)^2} \quad (N) \end{aligned}$$

2. Integral and Line length

There are three methods for representing integral in line length:

(i) Inside Triangle Method

Physically: Suppose a curve is represented by a straight line and that straight line has x and y components so that straight line with its components is looking like a right angle triangle then the curvature of the curve is represented by straight lines inside the triangle each with its x and y components which are being summed. These small curvature straight lines appear inside triangle and hence gives together curvature of straight line by which you can get a curve. It is a way of splitting curve into straight lines. In this way you have successfully converted integral into line length.

Mathematically:

$$A = \Delta x_o \Delta y_o + \sum_{n-1} \Delta x_{n-1} \Delta y_{n-1}$$

(ii) Boundary Triangle Method

Physically: Suppose a curve is represented by a straight line and that straight line has x and y components so that straight line with its components is looking like a right angle triangle then the curvature of the curve is represented by straight lines along the x and y components of the triangle or at the boundary of the triangle which are being summed. These small curvature straight lines appear at triangle boundary and hence gives together curvature of straight line by which you can get a curve. It is a way of splitting curve into straight lines. In this way you have again successfully converted integral into line length by Boundary Triangle Method.

Mathematically:

$$A = \Delta x_o \Delta y_o$$

Where

$$\Delta x_o = \Delta x_o + \sum_{n-1} \Delta x_{n-1}$$

$$\Delta y_o = \Delta y_o + \sum_{n-1} \Delta y_{n-1}$$

(iii) Outside Triangle Method

Physically: Suppose a curve is represented by a straight line and that straight line has x and y components so that straight line with its

components is looking like a right angle triangle then the curvature of the curve is represented by straight lines outside that triangle each straight line with its x and y components which are being summed. These small curvature straight lines appear outside triangle and hence gives together curvature of straight line by which you can get a curve. It is a way of splitting curve into straight lines. In this way you have again successfully converted integral into line length by Outside Triangle Method.

Mathematically:

$$A = \sum_n A_n$$

$$A = \sum_n \Delta x_n \Delta y_n$$

Combination(Curvature Separation Position Method)

Physically: Suppose a differential curve is represented by a differential straight line and that differential straight line has differential x and y components so that differential straight line with its differential components is looking like a right angle triangle then the curvature of the differential curve is represented by differential straight lines either inside triangle, at boundary or at outside triangle. These differential small curvature straight lines hence gives together curvature of differential straight line by which you can get a differential curve. It is a way of splitting differential curve into differential straight lines.

Mathematically:

$$A = \Delta x \Delta y$$

Applying limit on equation:

$$A = \lim_{\Delta x \rightarrow 0} \Delta x \Delta y$$

$$A = dx dy$$

Using the Inside triangle method in the Outside triangle method and adding boundary triangle method at the end.

$$A = \sum_n A_n$$

$$A = \sum_n dx_n dy_n$$

$$A = \sum_n ((dx_o + \sum_{n-1} dx_{n-1})(dy_o + \sum_{n-1} dy_{n-1}))$$

Where

$$dx_o = dx_o + \sum_{m-1} dx_{m-1}$$

$$dy_o = dy_o + \sum_{m-1} dy_{m-1}$$

3.Faris' Approach

Physically: Since I have already shown how to convert Integral into line length and line length into derivative so now i am gonna show how to convert integral into derivative by combining both equations and this procedure is called Faris' Approach.

Mathematically:

$$A = \int_a^b y dx \quad (1)$$

$$A = \Delta x \Delta y$$

$$A = \lim_{\Delta x \rightarrow 0} \Delta x \Delta y$$

$$A = dx dy \quad (2)$$

Equating (1) and (2)

$$\int_a^b y dx = dx dy \quad (3)$$

Using Curvature Separation Position Method in (3)

$$\int_a^b y_o dx_o + \int_a^b y_{n-1} dx_o + \int_a^b y_o dx_{n-1} + \int_a^b y_{n-1} dx_{n-1}$$

$$= \sum_n ((dx_o + \sum_{n-1} dx_{n-1})(dy_o + \sum_{n-1} dy_{n-1}))$$

(Where

$$dx_o = dx_o + \sum_{m-1} dx_{m-1}$$

$$dy_o = dy_o + \sum_{m-1} dy_{m-1}$$

)

$$\int_a^b y_o dx_o + \int_a^b y_{n-1} dx_o + \int_a^b y_o dx_{n-1} + \int_a^b y_{n-1} dx_{n-1}$$

$$= \sum_n (dy_o dx_o + dx_o (\sum_{n-1} dy_{n-1})) + (\sum_{n-1} dx_{n-1}) dy_o + (\sum_{n-1} dy_{n-1}) (\sum_{n-1} dx_{n-1})$$

Put

$$\frac{l}{\sqrt{1+(\frac{dy}{dx})^2}} = dx$$

So

$$\int_a^b y_o dx_o + \int_a^b y_{n-1} dx_o + \int_a^b y_o dx_{n-1} + \int_a^b y_{n-1} dx_{n-1}$$

$$= \sum_n \left(\frac{l dy_o}{\sqrt{1+(\frac{dy_o}{dx_o})^2}} + \frac{l(\sum_{n-1} dy_{n-1})}{\sqrt{1+(\frac{\sum_{n-1} dy_{n-1}}{dx_o})^2}} + \frac{l dy_o}{\sqrt{1+(\frac{dy_o}{\sum_{n-1} dx_{n-1}})^2}} + \frac{l(\sum_{n-1} dy_{n-1})}{\sqrt{1+(\frac{\sum_{n-1} dy_{n-1}}{\sum_{n-1} dx_{n-1}})^2}} \right)_n$$

Four integrals on the right equals four terms on the right in sequence and each of the four equations has the same solution like this:

(Note:

If one just uses the Outside Triangle Method Equation by dropping the summation and hence ignoring other technical details of Curvature Separation Position Method and equating it to an integral and putting dx value from equation (N) then the same equation is obtained as while using Curvature Separation Position Method Equation that is told in a following manner.)

$$\int_a^b y_o dx_o = \frac{l dy_o}{\sqrt{1+(\frac{dy_o}{dx_o})^2}}$$

$$\left(\frac{1}{\int_a^b y_o dx_o} \right)^2 = \frac{1+(\frac{dy_o}{dx_o})^2}{(l dy_o)^2}$$

$$\left(\frac{1}{\int_a^b y \, dx}\right)^2 = \left(\frac{1}{l \, dy}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{dy}{dx}\right)^2 \left(\frac{1}{l \, dy}\right)^2$$

$$\left(\frac{1}{\int_a^b y \, dx}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{dy}{dx} \frac{1}{l \, dy}\right)^2 = \left(\frac{1}{l \, dy}\right)^2$$

$$\left(\frac{1}{\int_a^b y \, dx}\right)^2 = \left(\left(\frac{dy}{dx}\right)^2 + 1\right) \left(\frac{1}{l \, dy}\right)^2$$

$$\left(\frac{1}{\int_a^b y \, dx \frac{dy}{dx}}\right)^2 = \left(\frac{dx}{dy}\right)^2 \frac{\left(\left(\frac{dy}{dx}\right)^2 + 1\right)}{(l \, dy)^2}$$

$$\left(\frac{1}{\int_a^b y \, dx \frac{dy}{dx}}\right)^2 = \frac{1 + \left(\frac{dx}{dy}\right)^2}{(l \, dy)^2}$$

$$\left(\int_a^b y \, dx \frac{dy}{dx}\right)^2 = \frac{(l \, dy)^2}{\left(\frac{dx}{dy}\right)^2 + 1}$$

$$\left(\int_a^b y \, dx \frac{dy}{dx}\right)^2 = \frac{(l \, dy)^2}{\left(\frac{dx}{dy}\right)^2 + 1}$$

$$\left(\int_a^b y \, dx\right)^2 = \frac{(l)^2 (dy)^4}{(dx + dy)^2} \left(\frac{dx}{dy}\right)^2$$

$$\left(\int_a^b y \, dx\right)^2 = \frac{(l)^2 (dy)^2 (dx)^2}{(dx + dy)^2}$$

$$\int_a^b y \, dx = \frac{l \, dy \, dx}{dx + dy}$$

$$\frac{\int_a^b y \, dx}{\frac{dy}{dx}} = \frac{l \, (dx)^2}{dx + dy} \quad (4)$$

(4) is called Integral-Derivative Equation

(One can also write Integral-Derivative Equation combinely for those four integrals and completing the Curvature Separation Position Method but the meaning will be the same)

(4)Some Technical Insights

2. Integral and Line Length

(1) Prove of The Methods

If you want a proof of the methods that convert integral into line length then you can even add coordinate shift for straight lines that form curvature of straight line.

3. Faris' Approach

(1) Whole Curve Integral-Derivative Equation

Seriously speaking the procedure is the same to convert integral to derivative for the whole curve instead of just for a differential line you have to just take the double integral of the derived equation with x and y or double integral with x and y of the other two equations that are used in Faris' Approach.

(2) Using Integral-Derivative Equation in any situation

One can even use several formulae for the quantities in the resultant equation that convert integral to derivative if those quantities are not readily available in a particular situation.

(5) Conclusion

Integral is the fundamental operation in calculus and also derivative and they are convertible. One can convert integral or curve's area function into its differential slope function using the equation derived by Faris' approach.